

N-Salicylideneamino Acid Complexes of Nickel(II)

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Complexes of nickel(II) with Schiff bases derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde with the bidentate amino acids, DL-2-aminobutyric acid, β -alanine, 3-aminobutyric acid and 4-aminobutyric acid, and the potential tridentate amino acids, DL-asparagine and L-glutamine have been synthesised and characterised. The complexes are paramagnetic and may be assigned octahedral geometry both in solid state and in solution. The amide group in the tridentate amino acids does not appear to participate in coordination so that the Schiff bases derived from these are essentially similar to those obtained from the bidentate amino acids.

THE condensation of *o*-hydroxyaromatic aldehydes and bidentate amino acids, like glycine yields dianionic tridentate Schiff bases with an ONO donor set. Such ligands, because of their ability to form mono- as well as bis-complexes with 3*d*-block metal ions, yield complexes with different structural features. Schiff base complexes of *d*-block metal ions derived from α -amino acids have been investigated by several authors¹⁻⁵. Cobalt(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes of Schiff bases derived from α -, β - and γ -amino acids have been reported by Ramanujam and Sivasankar^{6,7}. The present paper reports the studies on nickel(II) complexes of Schiff bases derived from bidentate α -, β - and γ -amino acids and also from potentially tridentate amino acids.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes: The Schiff base complexes were prepared by reacting nickel(II) acetate with the preformed Schiff bases. To the appropriate amino acid (0.01 mol) dissolved in minimum amount of water, an aqueous alcoholic solution of salicylaldehyde (0.01 mol) was added and heated to 50°.

Solid nickel(II) acetate (0.01 mol) was added in small portions with constant stirring. The solid complex that separated out was collected on a filter, washed successively with water, alcohol and ether and dried *in vacuo*. The same complexes could also be prepared by reacting the appropriate amino acid with bis(salicylaldehyde)nickel(II) complex in aqueous alcoholic medium.

Analysis: Metal and nitrogen contents of the complexes were determined by EDTA titrations and Kjeldahl's method, respectively⁸. Carbon and hydrogen contents of a few representative complexes were determined at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

The ir spectra of the complexes in KBr pellets were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. Electronic absorption spectra in methanol and diffuse reflectance spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P instrument. Conductance measurements were carried out in methanol using a Toshniwal direct reading conductance bridge provided with a cell of cell constant

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF NICKEL COMPLEXES

Complex	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
	M	N	C	H	
Ni(Sal.Tab.2H ₂ O)	19.10 (19.44)	4.50 (4.63)			3.40
Ni(Sal. β -ala.2H ₂ O)	20.00 (20.39)	4.50 (4.86)	40.80 (41.70)	4.70 (4.86)	3.30
Ni(Sal.Bab.2H ₂ O)	18.90 (19.44)	4.80 (4.63)			3.35
Ni(Sal.Fab.2H ₂ O)	19.30 (19.44)	4.70 (4.63)	44.00 (43.71)	4.50 (4.30)	3.45
Ni(Sal.Aspg.2H ₂ O)	17.50 (17.74)	8.20 (8.46)	43.10 (43.54)	4.60 (4.84)	3.30
Ni(Sal.Glg.2H ₂ O)	17.10 (17.02)	7.90 (8.12)			3.25

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0.666. Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out using a Stanton automatic derivatograph with a heating rate of 5 to 6° min⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The nickel(II) complexes of the Schiff bases derived from bidentate and tridentate amino acids are light green in colour and are insoluble in water and common organic solvents. They are partially soluble in alcohol and in coordinating solvents, like DMF, DMSO and pyridine *N*-salicylidene-4-aminobutyronickel(II) is totally insoluble in any of the above solvents. The stoichiometric composition of all the complexes was found to be NiSB.2H₂O (Table 1).

The infrared spectra of all the complexes show a broad band centered around 3 350 cm⁻¹ and this has been assigned to the O—H stretch of the coordinated water molecules. Supporting evidence for this assignment has been obtained from thermogravimetric studies, the complexes losing the water molecules around 150°. The ν_{C-N} stretch of the imino group is observed around 1 650 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes. The asymmetric stretch of the carboxyl group overlaps on the absorption of the phenyl ring at 1 600 cm⁻¹ while the symmetric stretch of the carboxyl group is observed around 1 420 cm⁻¹.

Conductance measurements of the complexes in methanol indicate them to be non-electrolytes. This is in accordance with the expectation of the participation of two monoanionic groups, namely the carboxyl and the phenoxy, in coordination. Magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate the complexes to be paramagnetic, the observed magnetic moments ranging from 3.3 to 3.5 B.M. at room temperature.

The electronic absorption spectra in methanolic solution and diffuse reflectance spectra of the solid Schiff base complexes derived from both the bidentate and tridentate amino acids are found to be similar. The spectra of the present set of complexes are comparable with those of the octahedral complexes of nickel(II) and exhibit three transitions in the visible and near-infrared regions. The low energy absorption is observed as a broad band centred around 11 000 cm⁻¹ and has been assigned to the ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ transition. The two bands which appear at 15 500 and 25 000 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P)

transitions, respectively. The last band appears only as a shoulder because of the more intense charge-transfer spectra occurring in the same region. Besides these bands, a weak absorption appearing as a shoulder around 13 500 cm⁻¹ may possibly be assigned to the forbidden transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$. The electronic absorption and the diffuse reflectance spectra of the individual complexes are similar indicating the similarity in the geometries in the solid state and in solution.

Structure : On the basis of spectral and magnetic data it is obvious that nickel(II) is octahedrally coordinated. The analytical data indicated a composition of NiSB.2H₂O giving a total number of five coordination sites. A dimeric structure involving bridging by carboxyl oxygens and the apical coordination of water molecules leading to an overall octahedral coordination around the central metal ion may be envisaged. A similar structure has been proposed for cobalt(II)^{5,6}, manganese(II)³ and nickel(II)⁹ complexes.

It is interesting to note that the Schiff base complexes derived from β - and γ -amino acids also retain a geometry similar to that of the *N*-salicylidene- α -amino acid complexes. The seven-membered ring in *N*-salicylidene-4-aminobutyronickel(II) is apparently stabilised by its fusion to a six-membered one, though a seven-membered chelate ring is not stable as such in complexes of 3d-block metal ions. The presence of additional coordination sites, namely, the amide group in asparagine and glutamine moieties of the Schiff bases have apparently no effect on the geometry or the composition of the complexes.

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